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Assessment Of The Burden Of *Candidiasis* (Toilet Diseases) Colonization And Transmission Amongst Female Students Living In Female Hostels of Kebbi state University of Science and Technology, Aliero

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ABSTRACT

The prevalence of candidiasis varies between populations, with differences in epidemiological features, the reasons for the difference are still unknown and the related risk factors remained unclear. Microscopic examination of HVS was carried out, Gram-staining and fungal culture and questioner was administered. Further confirmation by on chromogenic medium (CHROMagar Candida; Difco BBL, USA) was carried out and commercial biochemical identification kit (API 20C AUX; bioMérieux, Lyon, France). This study indicated that 255 (87.33%) out of 292 HVS were positive with at least one *Candida* species. Out of 345 total *Candida* species, *Candida albicans* (n=207, 60.0%) was found to be the most common species, followed by *C. tropicalis* (n=37, 10.7%), *C. parapsilosis* (n=27, 7.8%), *C. glabrata* (n=25, 7.2%), *Cryptococcus neuformance* (n=18, 5.2%), *Trichosporun asahi* (n=16, 4.6%), *Candida krusei* (n=11, 3.2%), *Candida rugose* (n=2, 0.6%) and *C. guilliermondii* (n=2, 0.6%). *C. albicans* was also associated with both single infection (132/173, 76.3%) and multiple *Candida* species infections (75/82, 91.5%). High Prevalence of *C. albicans* with slight predominance of *C. tropicalis* over *C. albicans* was observed suggestive of alarming rate of *Candidiasis* in KSUSTA female students. The most prevalent (burden) *Candida* species in KSUSTA are *C. albicans*, *C. tropicalis*, *C. Parapsilosis* and *C. glabrata* (from highest to low). The number of mixed *Candidal* infections is higher among the population of between 35 to 45 age group, while between the age group of 18 to 25.

Keywords: *Candidiasis*; burden; KSUSTA Female students

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Candidiasis is a common Women fungal infection caused by *Candida* species, mainly *Candida albicans*. It is one of the most frequent superficial mycoses in Women. Three (3) out of four (4) women experience

Candidiasis at least once, while one (1) in two (2) get it twice or more during their lifetime. It is characterized by inflammatory signs and symptoms detected in the vulva and vaginal mucosa that are caused and linked by an overgrowth of *Candida* species, which are generally present as quiescent vaginal commensals in 20 -50% of Women (Pereira , 2018). This disease is associated with high morbidity, economic costs, sexually transmitted infections, and ascending genital tract diseases, leading to infertility. Signs and symptoms of the disease includes: Irritation, edema, itching, dysuria, burning with urination. The predisposing factors for both *albicans* and non *albicans* candidiasis are pregnancy, diabetes mellitus and the use of broad-spectrum antibiotics (Ahmad *et al.*, 2009) as well as oral contraceptives with high oestrogen content (Akah *et al.*, 2002). Furthermore, poorly supported risk factors include use of sponge, intrauterine devices, diaphragm, condoms, Oragenital sex, douching and intercourse (Glover *et al.*,2003) and diet with high glucose content (De leon *et al.*,2002).Vaginal discharges, pain during sex, fissures in the vulva and perineum, and redness around the vagina. According to epidemiological studies, the prevalence of candidiasis varies between populations. Even in similar population groups, the epidemiological features of this infection are different. The reasons for the difference in the epidemiology of Candidiasis among various population such as University communities are still unknown and the related risk factors remained unclear. Annually, thousands of students register with KSUSTA as new-intake and returning student from across the Nigeria for Undergraduates, Postgraduates and Diploma programs. Female students constitutes substantial number of these candidates and majority of them are residing in KSUSTA hostels and share common hostel toilets. Overcrowding, Socio-demography, Social-life style and poor hygienic conditions of residence increase the risk of colonization and transmission of Candidiasis among women. The KSUSTA University clinic and General Hospital Aliero frequently received and treat Female students presenting cases related to Vulvo-vaginal infections. Hence, this study is intended to assess the prevalence and burden of this diseases among female students of KSUSTA. The knowledge of the etiologic pathogens for Candidiasis and how it related to overcrowding, environment hygienic conditions and social life style would be useful towards the prevention and control of the diseases among the female student in the hostels. The aim of this research is to determine the prevalence (Burden) of Candidiasis among Female student residing on KSUSTA campus female hostels, to identify the most prevalent candida species among KSUSTA female students, and to find out whether the prevalence of Candidiasis among KSUSTA female student is associated with student's social life style on Campus.

2.0. METHODOLOGY

1.1 Study area and study design

This study was conducted at Kebbi State University of Science and Technology, Aliero (KSUSTA) in the period of January to August 2024. KSUSTA has a total of eight student's accommodation facilities (hostel), out of which five for female. Each female hostel consisting of an estimated 40 rooms and two big toilets (Each big toilet consists of 10 units of toilets), and the toilets are routinely cleaned twice a day (morning and evening). In each of the forty (40) rooms there are four occupants, often with more than four as squatters.

2.2 Inclusion and Exclusion criteria

This study considered only KSUSTA female students living on-campus. Any female student living in any of the female KSUSTA on-campus hotels and who agreed to participate in this study were recruited. Any female student not living on-campus hostels or living in KSUSTA on-campus hostel but not agreed to participate in this study were excluded.

2.3 Participant recruitment and sample collection

This study is a cross-sectional descriptive study designed to be carried out between January to August 2024, involving twenty (200) participants. KSUSTA Female students who consented for the study in any of the KSUSTA student female hostel were randomly selected. Each participant was given a questionnaire and informed consent form to fill, and vaginal swab sample were collected from same participant. Detailed information of the participants were gathered such as: Virginal discharge, vaginal itching, use of tight panties, use of contraceptives, indiscriminate use of antibiotics and age group.

2.4 Identification of Candidate species

Significant *Candida* growth was defined as presence of pure or predominant growth of *Candida spp* on fungal culture media from HVS. All resulting colonies observed on CHROMagar were identified by colony morphology and pigmentation according to the manufacturer's instructions and as described by Odds and Bernaerts (3). Isolates from SDA and PDA, as well as CHROMagar plates, were also confirmed by Isolates were identified to a species level using a chromogenic medium (CHROMagarCandida; Difco BBL, USA) as well as a commercial biochemical identification kit (API 20C AUX; bioMérieux, Lyon, France).

2.5 Statistical analysis

Data were entered and analyzed using Microsoft Excel 2016 for the frequency of *Candida* species. Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS, Chicago) Version 24.0 was used to analyze the association of positive *Candida* isolates with the participant's socio-demographics and symptoms. This was done using Pearson chi-square test and Fisher's exact test, where *p* value of less than 0.05 was considered to be significant.

RESULTS

From the total of 345 participants in this study, 272 with complete demographic data and symptomatic Virginal Candidiasis records were reported in this study. All of the participants were resident of KSUSTA on-Campus. Their age ranged from 18 to 45 years old with the mean \pm standard deviation of 57.4 ± 9.7

The Virginal swabs culture results for the 297 were summarized in Table 1. Briefly, 255 (87.3%) of the cultured swabs were positive for *Candida* species, by which the frequencies of single and multiple *Candida* species were 173 (67.8%) and 82 (32.2%), respectively. The distribution of *Candida* species isolated in this study showed that *Candida albicans* (n=207, 60%) was predominant among a total of 345 isolates, comprising both single and multiple isolates. *C. albicans* was also found to be the commonest pathogen (n=132, 76.3%) in a total of 173 single isolates. The frequencies of *C. albicans* associated with multiple isolates of two, three and four types of *Candida* were 62 (48.4%), 11 (30.6%) and 2 (25.0%), respectively.

Other types of *Candida* species isolated from the Virginal swab culture include *C. tropicalis* (n=37, 10.7%), *C. parapsilosis* (n=27, 7.8%), *C. glabrata* (n=25, 7.2%), *Cryptococcus neoformans* (n=18, 5.2%), *Trichosporon asahi* (n=16, 4.6%), *Candida krusei* (n=11, 3.2%), *Candida formata* (n=2, 0.6%) and *Candida guilliermondii* (n=2, 0.6%). Most of these *Candida* species were seemed to present with combination as either dual, triple or quadruple isolates (Table 1). On the other hand, *Candida albicans* and *Candida tropicalis* were mostly found as single isolates.

Of the multiple specie (Table 2), most of the species combination of dual isolates was dominated by *C. albicans* and *C. tropicalis* (n=19, 27.5%). *C. albicans* and *C. tropicalis* also dominated in triple (n=7, 63.6%) and quadruple (n=2, 100%) species along with the presence of other bacteria. Apart from *C. albicans* was found to present with other *Candida* such as *Candida parapsilosis*, *Candida krusei*, *Candida guilliermondii* and *Candida famata*. Interestingly, *Candida tropicalis* was also detected in all triple and quadruple *Candida* species. In contrast to *Candida tropicalis*, *Candida guilliermondii* was only found in the specimens as multiple isolates. Whilst, *C. glabrata* and *C. famata*, were found negative in this study, even though they are among the commonest *Candida* species associated with Candidiasis.

This study revealed that the use of contraceptives and pregnancy is one of the major factors predisposing Females to Candidiasis. In this study, most of the respondent claimed to present with Virginal itching (n=270; 99.3%), either alone or in combination with other symptoms (Table 3). With regards to the Virginal discharge (53.9%) and indiscriminate use of antibiotics (52.6%) among participants, age group between 25 - 35 showed higher frequency of isolation comparing to age group of 18-25 years. Conversely, symptoms of Virginal rashes (55.6%) and Virginal discharge (51.5%) were observed to be higher among the age group of 35-45 years. In addition, Female students of higher age group of 35 to 45 years old were seemed to acquire the symptoms of itching, discharge and Virginal rashes, more than the others (Table 3). However, all the Virginal Candidiasis symptoms, excluding rashes (*p* value = 0.021), were not statistically significant to be influenced by either age groups.

Regarding the association of age groups and *Candidiasis* symptoms with *Candida* species infections, high acquisition of *Candida* infections was found among all age groups defined in this study, ranging from 77.3% to 96.0%. A progressive increase of *Candida* infection was observed in correspondence with the increment of age group (Table 4). Although not statistically significant, it was noted that 96% of the participants of age more than 35 years old (n = 50) acquired with at least one *Candida* infection during the period of study. Moreover, all the six participants of age above 35 years old were positive with *Candida* species. Overall, above 80% of the participants who had presence with any of the *Candidiasis* symptoms were positive with at least single *Candida* species. However, the results showed that age groups and symptoms were not significantly associated with *Candida* infections.

RESULTS

Table 1: Frequencies of *Candida* species isolation as single and multiple species in female KSUSTA Students

Candida species	Single species (n=173)	Multiple species (n = 82)			Total sample (n=292)
		2 species (n=69)	3 species (n=11)	4 species (n=2)	
<i>Candida albicans</i>	132	62	11	2	207
<i>Candida tropicalis</i>	11	17	7	2	37
<i>Candida parapsilosis</i>	2	17	7	1	27
<i>Candida glabrata</i>	20	5	-	-	25
<i>Cryptococcus neoformans</i>	2	11	4	1	18
<i>Trichosporon asahi</i>	3	11	2	-	16
<i>Candida krusei</i>	2	4	4	1	11
<i>Candida famata</i>	1	1	-	-	2
<i>Candida rugose</i>	0	0	1	1	2
<i>Candida guilliermondii</i>					
Total Candida species	173	128	36	8	345

Table 2: Frequency of isolation of *Candida albicans* along with other *Candida* species among Female KSUSTA Student

	Co-infection with multiple <i>Candida</i> species				Sample counts (n)
	Organism I	Organism II	Organism III	Organism IV	
Dual isolates (n=69)	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>C. tropicalis</i>			19
	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>C. glabrata</i>			16
	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>C. krusei</i>			14
	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>C. tropicalis.</i>			9
	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>C. parapsilosis</i>			4
	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>C. guilliermondii</i>			4
	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>Cryptococcus neuformans</i>			1
	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>Candida famata</i>			1
	<i>C. albicans.</i>	<i>Candida rugose</i>			1
Triple isolates (n=11)	<i>C. albicans.</i>	<i>C. tropicalis</i>	<i>C. parapsilosis</i>		3
	<i>C. albicans.</i>	<i>C. glabrata</i>	<i>C. tropicalis.</i>		2
	<i>C. albicans.</i>	<i>C. krusei</i>	<i>C. parapsilosis</i>		2
	<i>C. albicans.</i>	<i>C. tropicalis.</i>	<i>C. glabrata</i>		2
	<i>C. albicans.</i>	<i>C. parapsilosis</i>	<i>C. krusei</i>		1
	<i>C. albicans.</i>	<i>C. guilliermondii</i>	<i>C. tropicalis</i>		1
Quadruple isolates (n=2)	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>C. tropicalis</i>	<i>C. parapsilosis</i>	<i>C. glabrata</i>	1
	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>Parapsilosis</i>	<i>C. guilliermondii</i>	<i>C. krusei</i>	1
	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>C. glabrata</i>	<i>C. krusei</i>	<i>C. tropicalis</i>	1
Total Female Students with multiple <i>Candida</i> infections					82

Table 3: The association of the frequencies of occurrence of Candida isolate with diseases symptoms

Symptoms	Candida Isolates						Chi-square test (df)	p value*
	18-25		26-30		31- 35			
	n=22 (%)	(%)	n=200 (%)	(%)	n=50 (%)	(%)		
Virginal discharge	Yes	7 (7.1)	72 (72.7)	20 (20.2)			0.493	0.781 [†]
	No	15 (8.7)	128 (74.0)	30 (17.3)			(1)	
Virginal itching	Yes	22 (8.1)	198 (73.3)	50 (18.5)			0.725	0.696 [†]
	No	0 (0)	2 (100)	0 (0)			(2)	
Use of tight panties	Yes	12 (8.9)	98 (72.6)	25 (18.5)			0.247	0.884 [†]
	No	10 (7.3)	102 (74.5)	25 (18.2)			(2)	
Use of contraceptives	Yes	8 (9.8)	61 (74.4)	13 (15.9)			0.824	0.662 [†]
	No	14 (7.4)	139 (73.2)	37 (19.5)			(2)	
Indiscriminate use of antibiotics	Yes	7 (7.1)	72 (72.7)	20 (20.2)			0.493	0.781 [†]
	No	15 (8.7)	128 (74.0)	30 (17.3)			(1)	

(df) degree of freedom

*Significant level was set at 0.05

[†] Pearson chi-square test

[‡] Fisher's exact test

Table 4: The association of age groups with the frequency of occurrence of Candidiasis symptoms

Symptoms	Age groups						Chi-square test (df)	p value*
	18-25		26-30		31-35			
	n=22	(%)	n=200	(%)	n=50	(%)		
Virginal discharge	Yes	7 (7.1)	72 (72.7)	20 (20.2)			0.493 (1)	0.781 [†]
	No	15 (8.7)	128 (74.0)	30 (17.3)				
Virginal itching	Yes	22 (8.1)	198 (73.3)	50 (18.5)			0.725 (2)	0.696 [†]
	No	0 (0)	2 (100)	0 (0)				
Use of tight panties	Yes	12 (8.9)	98 (72.6)	25 (18.5)			0.247 (2)	0.884 [†]
	No	10 (7.3)	102 (74.5)	25 (18.2)				
Use of contraceptives	Yes	8 (9.8)	61 (74.4)	13 (15.9)			0.824 (2)	0.662 [†]
	No	14 (7.4)	139 (73.2)	37 (19.5)				

(df) degree of freedom

*Significant level was set at 0.05

[†] Pearson chi-square test

[‡] Fisher's exact test

DISCUSSION

Candida spp. are the most frequently isolated yeast in Volvo virginal infections. In this study 95% of the Yeast isolates were *Candida* species, with *Candida albicans* outnumbered *C. tropicalis* by 95% of the total *Candida* isolates, a trend observed in similar study in another tertiary institution in North central Nigeria, in 2016 were *C. albicans* is the most common *Candida* species in VVC among women followed by *C. glabrata* which has a higher prevalence among older women, slightly different from this study were *C. tropicalis* became the second. This study is the first of such, reporting on yeast isolates from KSUSTA, an Institution being a one of the densely populated institution in the Northwest region with high number of female student staying on-Campus. However, a study on Candidiasis cases from 2015 to 2016 at another tertiary institution in Southwestern, Nigeria by Tzar and Shamim [7] also found *C. tropicalis* to be the most frequent instead of *C. albicans* *Candida*, though *C. albicans* isolates were higher by 8%. Similarly, Ng and colleagues [8] also found *C. tropicalis* to be the most common *Candida* species isolated from blood next to *C. albicans*, among isolates from various specimens obtained between 2000 and 2013. *C. tropicalis* is indeed the leading non-*albicans* species in Asia and more so in tropical areas [20], when compared to other regions such as Europe, UK and USA [19]. In this study the significant association between *C. tropicalis* isolation and Socio-demographic factors (and vice versa with *C. albicans*) justifies the increased incidence of *C. tropicalis* as compared to *C. albicans* noted herein. The incidence of non-*albicans* *Candida* worldwide is generally observed to be increasing. Still, the proportion of non-*albicans* *Candida* among *Candida* species in populations-based studies done in various parts of the world seem to largely vary from 18.3% to 83.0% [19]. This variability between different geographical regions is caused by several factors, mostly due to different antifungal treatment practices, use of indwelling catheters, patient demographic features and chronic underlying diseases [18]. Increase in number of *C. glabrata* isolates on the other hand have been reported in Europe and USA, owing to the

extensive use of fluconazole as prophylaxis and treatment [19]. It is important to note that isolation of *Candida* from HVS should not be considered as a marker for Candidal vaginitis, as it among the normal flora of the tract. A study reported that no cases of *Candidiasis* was identified among age group of 18 - 25 female students with histopathological evidence of bacterial infection and high rate of *Candida* isolation from the age group of 35 – 45 women [21]. Although not significant, most (65.1%) of the *C. tropicalis* isolates found herein, were from age group of 25 - 35 women, a trend also reported elsewhere [6]. On the other hand, more than half of the *C. albicans* isolates (56.4%) were obtained from the age group of 26 - 31. *C. tropicalis* isolation from blood specimens was found to be significantly associated to Socio-demographic factors, while *C. albicans* was significantly negatively related. Similarly, a study revealed significantly lower occurrence of *C. albicans* in participants age group 18 – 25 when compared to participants age group 25 – 30; while non-*albicans* *Candida*, namely *C. krusei* and *C. glabrata* were more prevalent among the former [22]. Risk factors of Socio-demographic factors vary between species. Risk factors for *C. tropicalis* includes age, use of contraceptives, and indiscriminate use of antibiotics are significant risk factors for *C. glabrata* and *C. krusei*; while younger age and non-active sex ages 18 - 25 have been associated with *C. parapsilosis* infections [18].

CONCLUSIONS

The *Candida* isolates, mainly being *Candida* spp, isolated in the year 2024 at KSUSTA, Nigeria, were predominated by *C. albicans*. *C. albicans* was the most common species isolated in HVS. The antifungal resistance observed in the present study was mainly restricted to the azoles. All *Candida* species were highly susceptible to amphotericin B, the echinocandins and flucytosine. Lowest drug susceptibility was noted to itraconazole especially among *C. glabrata* and *C. tropicalis* isolates and to fluconazole among *C. glabrata* isolates. These findings emphasize the trend seen worldwide on increasing resistance to the azoles especially among the non-*albicans* *Candida* species. The opposite correlation seen in the present study between prevalence of *C. tropicalis* and *C. albicans* with underlying haematological disorders may have caused a higher incidence of azole-resistance in this clinical setting which warrants for a multicenter study in the future, for confirmation.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

We declare that the content of this manuscript has not been presented or published anywhere and all the authors has no objection.

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